

METHODS OF USING MODERN EDUCATIONAL TOOLS IN FORMING COMPUTER DEVICE SKILLS OF FUTURE TEACHERS.

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ANNOTATION This article presents the possibilities and recommendations for the use of modern teaching means in the formation of students' skills in computer devices.

Key words: computer devices, modern teaching means, computer science, Windows.

The widespread introduction of modern teaching means in the educational process imposes on students the task of regular independent study of computer science and information technology [1]. There is no doubt that the creation of these teaching means, their use in the education system will give good results [2]. The use of modern teaching means in the teaching of computer devices and their physical properties in the field of computer science in higher education, in particular, in the subject "Computer Support" is effective.

In this regard, in our country and the Commonwealth of Independent States, scientists like A.A. Abdukodirov, M.M. Aripov, M.H. Lutfillaev, N.I. Taylakov, U.M. Mirsanov, U.B. Bakhodirova, Yu.P. Gospodarik, V.A. Kuklev, E.N. Dronova, J.J. Karbozova, V.A. Kuklev, E.S. Matosov, A.V. Mukhamedshina, G.K. Nurgalieva, L.F. Solovev, M.P. Koor, A.D. Ongarbaeva, E.P. Chernyaeva, E.V. Yakushina have been conducted researches on the methodology of creating modern teaching means in teaching science, the theory and practice of their use.

According to the results of the analysis of the scientific works of these researchers, it was found that there is a need to use modern teaching means, especially virtual learning technologies (virtual labs, virtual video lectures, virtual visual means,

virtual stands), in teaching the physical properties of the computer in higher education institutions.

Virtual education is a modern educational environment that encourages and enhances students' creative thinking to present educational material visually with the help of simulation software and hardware, to create a virtual image of complex processes and events, to organize complex experimental processes in a virtual form and expand the didactic potential of independent learning, increases motivation for learning activities, acquires basic knowledge of science, systematizes them, to provide methodological assistance in the development of teaching materials in the independent work of students [3, 4]. Therefore, the use of virtual learning technologies in teaching the physical properties of computer devices is purposeful. This gives students the opportunity to teach the process and events on computer devices:

- Understanding the process of data exchange on computer devices;
- Electric distribution in computer devices and their movement;
- Hard disk data location;
- The principle of operation of the microprocessor and the process of logical computing;
- Random-access memory and data exchange with the Windows operating system;
- The process of spreading viruses to interaction with the Windows operating system and its applications, as well as through the computer's data carriers;

In conclusion, the use of modern teaching means, especially virtual learning technologies, is effective in teaching students the physical properties of the computer and the process of data exchange in it, as well as in the figurative presentation of the interaction of viruses. In this case, students will be able to visually study and observe the teaching materials related to science. As a result, students become more interested and motivated in this subject. At the same time, it helps to expand the scope of thinking and develop thinking.

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